

Annals of Medical & Clinical Research and Reviews (AMCRR)

Emotional Conflicts—Measuring the Harm of Doing Things You Don’t Want to Be Done to You

Maria Kuman, PhD

*Holistic Research Institute, Knoxville, TN 37923, US.

Correspondence: Maria Kuman, PhD
Holistic Research Institute, Knoxville, TN 37923, USA

Received: 2 Mar 2026; **Accepted:** 8 Mar 2026; **Published:** 16 Mar 2026

Citation: Emotional Conflicts-The Harm of Doing Things You Don’t Want to Be Done to You. Opinion Art. 2026; 1(1): 1-3.

Abstract

All living being (humans, animals, and plants) are material bodies and a living force, which is their field-half seen as aura. I found the aura to be nonlinear electromagnetic field (NEMF) and to be the one that makes us emotional and emotionally creative (there is no creativity without emotions). Thus, without our field-half, seen as aura, we would be very primitive creatures. We are emotional creatures, and our emotions influence the functioning of our material body. If so, expect whatever you do, through its emotional impact, to influence you-your emotional balance and your health. I have measured, and have the proof, that helping others improves our health. In this article, I am going to show that when we do things that we know are not good - harm others or take advantages of others - emotional conflict is present, which influences negatively our health.

Keywords: helping others boosts our health; harming others harms our health; emotional conflicts; emotional conflicts harm our health.

1. Introduction – Whatever You Do Reflects Back on You

We are a material body and emotional Spirit (seen as aura), which makes us emotional and creative (there is no creativity without emotions). Proof that we are material body and emotional Spirit is the fact that identical twins with the same DNA are totally different emotional personalities. And since we are material body and emotional Spirit – the health of our body depends equally on the food we eat and the emotions we feel (see sec. 2). Will our blood be acidic or alkaline depends on both – the type of food (alkaline or acidic) we consum, and on the emotions (positive or negative) we feel (sec. 2).

We are emotional creatures, and the emotions we feel are just as important as the food we eat. If the existence of the emotional Spirit is still questioned, it is because the field of the emotional Spirit (NEMFs) is 1,000 times

weaker than the field of the material body (NEMFm). However, the weak field of the Spirit rules and regulates everything in the material body, not with its strength, but with the information it carries. Since only nonlinear fields do not dissipate and can imprint information, the field of the Spirit must be and it is weak nonlinear electromagnetic field (NEMFs), - I had to develop a very sensitive equipment to be able to measure it .

Measurements with my sensitive equipment confirmed [1] that our subjective feeling that our Spirit feels uplifted when we have done something good is right - helping others boost our energy and improves our health [1]. In this article, I am going to show that when we do things, which we know are not good (like harm others, or take advantages of others) emotional conflict is present, which influences negatively our health.

That is why 8 different religions say the same: “Don’t do to others, what you don’t want to be done to you” [2]. If we all follow this simple rule, there wouldn’t be stress in our lives, and there wouldn’t be emotional conflicts (from not doing to others what we don’t want to be done to us), which lead to poor health or diseases.

2. How Our Emotions Influence Our Health

The HeartMath Institute in California [3] found that: 1. Negative emotions (sour mood) make the blood sour, and the sour blood is thicker, which the heart has difficulty to circulate. If so, expect people with thick blood and clogged arteries to have had one serious negative experience (or series of negative experiences) in their lives. But since we are a material body (which gets its energy from food) and emotional Spirit (which loses energy at negative emotions), thick blood could be a result of negative emotions as well as a result of eating dominantly acidic (Yin) food, which makes the blood acidic (thicker).

2. Positive emotions make the blood more alkaline, the alkaline blood is thinner, and the heart pumps it easier. But thin blood could also be a result of eating dominantly alkaline (Yang) food, which makes the blood alkaline (thinner) and thinner blood circulates better. Since studies showed that the effect of one negative emotion is compensated by 3 to 4 positive emotions [4], to avoid making our lives a constant hunt for positive emotions, we should do our best to avoid negative emotions (and avoid doing things that harm others), which create emotional conflicts, because we know that we have done something wrong.

Surprisingly, our scientists and medical doctors agree that stress (negative emotions) causes physical and mental diseases, but they refuse to acknowledge the important role emotions play in our health and life. Why? Because we built our science on measurements only - if something cannot be measured, it does not exist. And

our Emotional Half (called Spirit) is very weak nonlinear electromagnetic field (NEMFs) – 1,000 times weaker than the field of the material body NEMFm - and since the scientists cannot measure it, they deny it. However, our technology allows to build equipment sensitive enough to measure what emotions do to our body, and I have built one.

3. My Measurements of How Our Way of Thinking (Positive or Negative) Influences Our Health

All our thoughts are emotionally colored, which makes important not only the emotions we feel, but also the thoughts (positive or negative) we have. Below are the measurements with my sensitive equipment, which illustrate the importance of our way of thinking.

1. Positive thinking makes the body energy more balanced (upper curves), and since perfect balance means perfect health, positive thinking makes us healthy.
2. Negative thinking (lower curves) makes the energy of the body more unbalanced, which means less healthy (because the energy of the genetically inherited weak organ drops down maximum). This means that dominant negative thinking with time will damage the genetically-inherited weak organ - leading to either a chronic disease (“chronic” means “slow”, because it takes years for the disease to get established), or cancer (it depends on the genetic predisposition).

According to Fig. 1: 1/ For David, the genetically-inherited weak organs are heart and stomach (his father had heart problem, his mother stomach problem). 2/ For Martha, the genetically-inherited weak organ is thyroid gland (she said her mother had thyroid problem). 3/ For Joyce, the genetically-inherited weak organ is stomach (she said each time she gets upset, her stomach gets upset). 3/ For Norm, the genetically-inherited weak organ is heart and he said both his parents had heart troubles. 4/ For Charlie, the genetically-inherited weak organs were the sexual organs and he had prostate problem later in life.

Fig. 1: The energy was measured (with my supersensitive equipment) at the chain of alternating vortices (spinning clockwise) and anti-vortices (spinning counterclockwise) of the nonlinear electromagnetic field of our aura (Spirit) ($NEMF = NEMF_m + NEMF_s$) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2

Our aura (Spirit) NEMF and its chain of alternating vortices (spinning clockwise) and anti-vortices (spinning counterclockwise) along the backbone (called “chakras”) and their corresponding energy levels

4. Both the Material Body and the Emotional Spirit Equally Matter

This means that it matters what we eat and how much we exercise, but it equally matters how we think – positively or negatively. Positive emotions (or just positive thinking) make us healthy, while negative emotions (stress) (or just negative thinking) lead with time to a disease of the genetically-inherited weak

organ. If the cells of the genetically-inherited weak organ have poorly integrated biorhythms - chronic disease of the genetically-inherited weak organ will develop. If the field between the cells is genetically-inherited weak, stress (negative emotions or just negative thinking) will further decrease this field, which will lead to the formation of crystals that will disconnect the cells and lead to malignancy, i.e.

cancer. Considering this, we should do our best to avoid negative emotions and negative thinking [5].

Russian scientists found that when they decrease the field between the cells 10 times, crystals (shaped as stacked coins) appear between the cells [6], which disconnect the cells and they start to multiply fast, just as they do in a cut wound. But when in a cut wound the new cells are ruled by the current of regrowth (that starts at the cut) where to go, in the case of cancer they multiply senselessly, which is called malignancy. My measurements show that negative thinking (or negative emotions (stress)) decreases the energy (including the energy between the cells). Based on the Russian studies the decreased field leads to the formation of crystals between the cells. Considering all this, I claim that my measurements explain for the first time how stress (negative emotions or just negative thinking) cause cancer - it leads to the formation of crystals between the cells, which disconnect the cells, and they start to multiply senselessly, which is called malignancy.

5. Emotional Conflicts from Doing to Others What We Don't Want to Be Done to Us, which Damages Our Health and Shortens Our Life

A. We Were Created by Light Saturated with Love

My grandfather Kuman was in a state of clinical death and came back. I grew up with his story what the Creator God looks like. When he was pronounced clinically dead, his Spirit left the body but hover over the dead body for 3 days and 3 nights. He could see his dead body lying on the bed, he could hear the talks of the people around, but he couldn't talk because the talking is done through the material body. This continued for 3 days and 3 night – the time it takes for the material body to completely die out, so that the Spirit (which is magnetically attached to the field of the material body) can leave. Indeed, Russian scientists were able to detect the weak field of the Spirit up to 3 days and 3 nights after the person was pronounced clinically dead, but not later on [6].

When Grandpa Kuman's Spirit finally left, it traveled through a long dark tunnel with light at the end of the tunnel. When his Spirit finally arrived at the end of the tunnel, he saw that the light was not the light we see with our eyes – it was a different light and it was light saturated with Love. He felt so much loved by this Big Light that he was ready to merge to it, when an angel rushed toward him shouting: "No, it is not yet your time! You need to go back." And he saw himself back in his mate-

rial body. Intrigued, I spoke with many other people, who were in a state of clinical dead and came back – they were all telling the same story.

B. We Were Created to Be Like Our Creator – Loving, Forgiving, and Helping Others

We were created by our Creator to be like Him – Loving, Forgiving, Helping others, and to be creative like him. Not to trim our creativity, the Creator gave us freedom of choice (by putting everything related to the Spirit in the Subconscious), which is the biggest gift of the Creator to us. However, if we don't do what we were created to do (Loving, Forgiving, and Helping Others) - we are self-punishing ourselves, which is manifested with lost physical or mental health. But the Creator gave us a Logical Mind to analyze with the hope that one day we will figure it out why we have the physical or mental troubles.

C. The Emotional Conflict When We Are Not Loving, Forgiving, and Helping Others

Eight different religions say the same: "Don't do to others, what you don't want to be done to you?" And what happens when you do to others what you wouldn't want to be done to you? You suffer emotional conflict because you did what you were not supposed to do. You were supposed to "love, forgive, and help others". And this emotional conflict influences negatively your physical health and emotional balance, which we wrongly call mental disease. Thus, if you want to be healthy (physically and mentally) "do not do to others what you don't want to be done to you" and "love, forgive and help others".

D. The Emotional Conflict from Not Doing Right Damages Our Health and Shortens Our Life

Thus, trespassing the main requirement: "Love, forgive, and help others" (which includes the requirement: "Don't do to others what you don't want to be done to you") damages our health and shortens our life. If the people that live to be 120 years old have a regrowth of new teeth, this means that we were originally created to live much more than 120 years, but this could happen only if we "Love, Forgive, and Help Others" and "Don't do to others what we don't want to be done to us".

6. Conclusions

Based on my measurements, I explained how stress (negative emotions or just negative thinking) causes cancer – it decreases the field between the cells, which according to Russian studies leads to the formation of crystals between the cells [6]. This disconnects the cells, and they start to multiply fast, as they do in a cut wound. But while in a cut wound there is a current of regrowth that start at the cut to lead the new cells where to go, in the case of cancer the new cells multiply senselessly, which is called malignancy.

However, since we are a material body and emotional Spirit, beside from negative emotions and negative thinking, crystals between the cells (that lead to malignancy) can also be formed when the lymph liquid between the cells is too thick because of: 1/ improper food, 2/ lack of exercise (when the blood system has the heart to pump the blood, the lymph liquid is moved only when we exercise), and 3/ too many parasites in the body because they dump their exhost into the lymph system, which provides the liquid between the cells [7].

This article also explained that we were created to be like our Creator: “Loving, Forgiving, and Helping Others”, which means: “Not doing to others, what we don’t want to be done to us”. If we do to others what we don’t want to be done to us, we suffer Emotional Conflict

(from not doing the things right), which leads to a disease (physical or mental), and a few of such trespasses will lead to death. Thus, “Love, Forgive, and Help Others” and “Do not do to others what you don’t want to be done to you” because this is the only way to be healthy, happy, and live a long life.

References;

1. Kuman M. Measuring How Helping Others Boost Your Energy and Health. *Int Innov Clin Res Rev.* 2025; 1(2).
2. Kuman M. *Science Speaks of God.* Health and Happiness Books. 2005.
3. HeartMath Institute. Available from: www.HeartMathInstitute.org
4. Aktualnie Problemi Stressa. Kishinev. 1969 (Russ.).
5. Kuman M. Cancer Is Nonlinear Structural Disorder Caused by Stress. *Int J Complement Altern Med.* 2018; 11(6).
6. Maslov L, Kirpichnikova I (Ed.). *Info-Energy Medicine of the Future.* Moscow. 2016 (Russ.).
7. Kuman M. Nontrivial Approach to Insomnia, Cancer, and Alzheimer Diseases. *J Clin Immunol Microbiol.* 2024; 5(3).

Copyright: ©2026: Maria Kuman. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction.